

Broaden your Horizon!

Play with Semantics via a Knowledge Graph-based Approach

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Keywords: Lexical semantics, Knowledge Graph, Semantic Web, Word senses, User evaluation, Italian

Abstract: (Lexical) semantics is the study of the meaning of words by looking at either the word itself or exploring its neighborhood. Hence, lexicons, synonyms, and analogies can be easily represented as semantic networks, also known as knowledge graphs, to represent words and their connections. While knowledge graphs can be perceived as a natural and intuitive representation for modeling and exploring words, directly accessing them via standard query languages, such as SPARQL, is cumbersome, mainly for lay users. This article explores the possibility of “playing with semantics” via a knowledge graph-based approach to let end-users explore lexical-semantic relations without explicitly formulating SPARQL queries. We evaluated the accuracy and the coverage of users’ expectations by inquiring about 27 Italian native speakers and compared quantitative and qualitative results. According to the performed evaluation, knowledge graphs have the potential to fulfill users’ satisfaction, but multiple source results must be merged to guarantee high coverage and accuracy.

1 Questionnaire

This document reports the online questionnaire used to collect users’ replies by detailing questions and the reply format. It behaves as supplementary material for the article entitled “Broaden your Horizon! Play with Semantics via a Knowledge Graph-based Approach”, presented at the 16th International Conference on Computer Supported Education (CSEDU 2024).

Participant’s profile.

- **Region of provenance** choosing among the list of Italian regions;
- **Gender**, choosing among *female*, *male*, *other/I prefer to not say it*;
- **Age range**, choosing among slots of 5 years each from underage to over fifty;
- **level of education** choosing among primary school, secondary school, high school, three- or five-year degree, postgraduate specialization;
- **working position** as free text;

- **interest in using a sophisticated vocabulary**, using a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 as the maximum;
- **auto-assessed level of preparation in the Italian language**, using a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 as the maximum.

Word senses. For each word, provide us with all the word meanings you can come up with autonomously, without any support. Then, rate all the proposed word senses using 0 to rate out-of-context suggestions, 0.5 for partially related meaning, and 1 for fully accurate suggestions.

- Write all the word senses attached to *tree*.
- Assess the accuracy of the following meanings attached to *tree*:
 - plant
 - ship mast
- Write all the word senses attached to *field*.
- Assess the accuracy of the following meanings attached to *field*:
 - battlefield
 - harvest field, such as paddy field
 - magnetic field
 - extermination or concentration camp

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- playing fields, such as a football or golf pitch
- field of action
- Write all the word senses attached to *organ*.
- Assess the accuracy of the following meanings attached to *organ*:
 - press organ
 - body organ
 - organ-matrix
 - eyesore
 - sensory organ
- Write all the word senses attached to *time*.
- Assess the accuracy of the following meanings attached to *time*:
 - weather
 - measurement of time (week, day, hour, second)
- Write all the word senses attached to *star*.
- Assess the accuracy of the following meanings attached to *star*:
 - starfish
 - cinema star
 - given name
 - celestial body
 - poinsettia in botany
- Write all the word senses attached to *heart*.
- Assess the accuracy of the following meanings attached to *heart*:
 - cardiac organ
 - city center
- Write all the word senses attached to *sun*.
- Assess the accuracy of the following meanings attached to *sun*:
 - sunglasses
 - solar eclipse
 - celestial body
 - sunstroke
- Write all the word senses attached to *peach/fishing*, (both *pesca* in Italian)
- Assess the accuracy of the following meanings attached to *peach/fishing*:
 - fishing as a job
 - peach tree
 - fish
 - *paurara*, name of a net used by fishermen in an Italian gulf
 - peach

- Write all the word senses attached to *belief/cupboard*, (both *credenza* in Italian).
- Assess the accuracy of the following meanings attached to *belief/cupboard*:
 - popular belief
 - cupboard
 - legend
- Write all the word senses attached to *wing*.
- Assess the accuracy of the following meanings attached to *wing*:
 - sport
 - hat
 - planes

Overall quantitative and qualitative assessment.

- *I felt inspired by the proposed meanings* giving a rate using a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 as the maximum.
- *I felt satisfied by the proposed meanings* giving a rate using a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 as the maximum.
- *I believe that the proposed meanings are original and interesting* giving a rate using a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 as the maximum.
- *I believe that the proposed meaning is exhaustive* giving a rate using a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 as the maximum.
- *Do you see any application context for this proposed approach and tool?*, as a free text.
- **General comments** as a free text.